

EUROqCHARM

EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution

Deliverable 5.2

First Year Report on Communication, Dissemination and Networking Activities

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Nature of the deliverable		
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DEC	Websites, patents, filing, etc.	
DEM	Demonstrator	
O	Other	

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CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
PU	Public	x

About EUROqCHARM

This deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Action programme under Grant Agreement 101003805 (EUROqCHARM).

Plastic pollution has become a global environmental and societal concern in recent years. Numerous protocols have been developed to monitor plastic debris, but these are rarely comparable. This has hindered gathering of knowledge regarding pollution sources, development of monitoring programmes and risk assessments and implementation of mitigation measures. To develop long-term solutions to reduce plastic pollution, it is essential to establish harmonised methodologies. EUROqCHARM will address this by critically reviewing state-of-the-art analytical methods and, taking harmonisation one step further, validating them through an interlaboratory comparison (ILC) study. This will bring together prominent laboratories in environmental plastics analysis and will produce certified reference materials to be marketed for at least three of the four target matrices (water, soil/sediment, biota, air), during and after project completion.

EUROqCHARM recognises that harmonisation for large scale monitoring requires flexibility, comparability and reliability. We will identify Reproducible Analytical Pipelines (RAP), resulting in a catalogue of RAP procedures for nano-, micro- and macro-plastics for the four target matrices. Each RAP will be validated in terms of Technology Readiness Level to decide if further validation is needed (by ILC).

Blueprints for standards, recommendations for policy and legislation and support for the establishment of acceptable reference levels and environmental targets will be given. This will include a roadmap for harmonised data collection and management, where policy analysis and coherence will be integral parts. To maximise impact, EUROqCHARM will also establish and consolidate an operational network for plastic monitoring, stimulating Transnational Joint Actions built on existing and future European and international initiatives.

The multi-stakeholder composition of EUROqCHARM puts the group in a unique position to achieve these ambitious goals.

More information on the project can be found at: www.EUROqCHARM.eu

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Executive Summary

Communication, dissemination and networking is an integral component of the EUROqCHARM project. A Communication and Dissemination Strategy was developed by the Communication and Coordination Committee. This forms the foundations of EUROqCHARM's work surrounding communicating within and outside of the project, dissemination and networking. All of the activities surrounding dissemination and networking fall under Work Package 5 – Knowledge transfer and dissemination

The first-year report on communication, dissemination and networking provides an overview of all the dissemination, communication and networking activities carried out by the project partners during the first year of the project. It outlines the communication and dissemination framework and presents the tools and activities that were undertaken to accomplish the set objectives.

The document is subdivided into 3 sections:

- The first section on “Communication and Dissemination Framework” provides relevant background information about the project and the role of communication and dissemination in achieving the project goals. This includes a description of the targeted audience and the project organs and groups that are most relevant.
- The second section on “Communication, Dissemination and Networking Activities” provides a report, structured following the Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan, on the activities carried out during the first project year. This chapter provides information on how the communication and dissemination is organised within the project, and what procedures are in place to achieve a continued and quality-controlled operation. Additionally, the plan for activities in the different areas during the second project year is provided.
- The concluding section highlights the major achievements during the first project year and provides a summary of the activities planned for the following year.

The structure of this deliverable will be maintained across the analogous deliverables to be prepared at the end of the second and third year of the project. These three yearly reports together with Deliverable 5.1 on the “Launch and Management of Dedicated Website and Social Media” conform the reporting deliverables due for WP5. Deliverable 5.1 includes, as an annex, the working version of the “Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan”. Deliverable 5.1 thus provides detailed information that is relevant for readers of the present document that wish to deepen their understanding on some of the elements referred here.

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List of Abbreviations, Acronyms and Partner Codes

Abbreviation	Definition
CCC	Communication and Coordination Committee
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSDP	Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan
ILC	InterLaboratory Comparison
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
RAP	Reproducible Analytical Pipelines
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SC	Steering Committee
SSAB	Stakeholders and Standardisation Advisory Board
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Acronyms	Definition
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation
EC	European Commission
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
EU	European Union
ISO	International Organisation for Standards
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NORMAN	Network of reference laboratories, research centres and related organisations for monitoring of emerging environmental substances
OSPAR	Oslo-Paris Convention
SETAC	Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry
UN	United Nations

Partner code	Full partner name
NIVA	Norwegian Institute for Water Research
CNR-ISMAR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Istituto di Scienze Marine)
VU	Free University Amsterdam (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam)
IFREMER	Institut Francais De Recherche Pour L'Exploration de la Mer
NIMRD	Institutul National de Cercetare-Dezvol Marine Grigore Antipa
SALT	-
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior Deinvestigaciones Cientificas
NILU	Norwegian Institute for Air Research
ILVO	Flemish Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (Instituut voor landbouw- en Visserijonderzoek)
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz- zentrum fur Polar- und Meeresforschung
AU	Aarhus University
Chiron	-
EAWAG	Eidgenoessische Anstaly Fuer Wasserversorgung Abwasserreinigung und gew
OGS	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale
AFNOR	Association Francaise de Normalisation

1. Communication and Dissemination Framework

1.1. Short Description of the Project

EUROqCHARM is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project funded under the EC Horizon 2020 Programme which started in November 2020 and will run over three years.

The overall objective of EUROqCHARM is to develop optimised, validated, and harmonised methods for assessment and monitoring of plastics in the environment, as well as blueprints for standards and recommendations for policy and legislation.

EUROqCHARM is aiming to **co-develop** methods and recommendations using a **multi-stakeholder approach**, whereby the project is structured to **bring together relevant stakeholders to enable cooperation and participation in the dialogue, decision making and implementation** of solutions. This step is critical, as the necessary developments require the **engagement and collaboration of researchers and various stakeholders** with a thorough understanding of the complexity arising from the wide array of polymer types and particle sizes dispersed in different environmental matrices. To this end, the **EUROqCHARM partners, advisory board members and associated stakeholders include all relevant research areas** (natural sciences devoted to marine, surface, groundwater, drinking and waste water, soil, air; analytical chemistry etc.), **industry** (instrument manufacturers, plastic producers and commercial laboratories), **regulators and policy makers** - United Nations (UN), EU and national level, **standardisation bodies, professional associations and societies, and national and international Non-Governmental Organisations** (NGOs). This sets EUROqCHARM in a unique position to coordinate the validation of the available methods and production of harmonised protocols for assessing plastic contamination that are also accessible to less-developed countries.

In order to reflect the complexity of the harmonisation procedures for plastic pollution monitoring and assessment, EUROqCHARM is structured into seven tightly inter-linked Work Packages (WP1-7). All WPs have strong relationships with one another, such that they can build on each other's outputs and there are no stand-alone WPs. The project activities are distributed across 7 Work Packages (WPs), each one with a defined scope and objective (Figure 1). The first three WPs are content generating work packages building on each other, and therefore becoming progressively more active and communications relevant, as the project timeline advances. WP4, devoted to capacity building, will make use of the outputs of the previous three work packages and is naturally communication and dissemination intensive. The last three WPs entail activity sustained through the whole project life.

The EUROqCHARM approach also highlights the importance of communication and dissemination activities to engage as many stakeholders from the very beginning. A sustained stakeholder engagement will determine the success of the project and largely condition the uptake of methodologies and recommendations across various domains: academia and research, standardisation, businesses, and policy.

Figure 1. The overall WPs structure of EUROqCHARM

1.2. Communication Objectives and Target Audiences

Communication and dissemination products and activities within EUROqCHARM aim to (i) ensure that all target audiences are effectively engaged and (ii) uptake of the project results so the effect/impact of the effort put in harmonizing methodologies is long lasting and allows to overcome the comparability challenge. The promotion of the use of harmonized methods, including survey design and sample collection, sample/specimen preparation, analytical detection, plastic quantification, and data reporting, through knowledge transfer and capacity building will ensure the achievement of the project results.

Specifically, WP5: **Knowledge Transfer and Dissemination**, is ensuring targeted communication, dissemination, and exploitation of project results.

The specific communication and dissemination objectives are:

- I. Ensure awareness of the project, objectives, and activities by the project stakeholders
- II. Allow engagement of stakeholders in activities relying on stakeholder engagement and providing legitimation for advancing in the project strategy
- III. Disseminate project results

EUROqCHARM specifically targets research and academia, commercial and public laboratories, analytical instrument manufacturers, standardisation organizations, monitoring bodies and networks, environmental data managers, policy makers and civil society organizations directly or indirectly engaged in assessment and monitoring of plastic pollution, as well as plastic policy development.

Many stakeholders pertaining to the categories named above have already been engaged by the Consortium, some even already during the project proposal development phase and, during the first year of the project. The stakeholders targeted belong to the following groups for which details are given further on in this report:

- The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)
- The Stakeholders and Standardisation Advisory Board (SSAB) which is divided in two groups, the Industrial Stakeholder Board and the Standardisation Stakeholder Board
- Associated laboratories interested to participate in interlaboratory comparison (ILC) exercises to validate processing methods ILC
- Research and academia stakeholders participating in events where EUROqCHARM has been presented or presented results such as virtual conferences, webinars and workshops
- Stakeholders participating in projects represented at cluster groups gatherings, such as those arranged by EU DG Environment, UNEP etc.

In addition to the specific stakeholders involved through the bodies and groups named above stakeholder mapping per Work Package (WP) is being conducted to complete the database of relevant EUROqCHARM stakeholders. Of specific interest for this is Task 5.5 devoted to “**Coordinating collaboration with other ongoing activities within the EU**” and Task 4.2 and its corresponding deliverable D4.2 “**Handbook of relevant European plastic monitoring entities, projects and initiatives**”.

EUROqCHARM is a highly specialized and technical CSA project and so is the bulk of the project audience. Still, because EUROqCHARM is aimed at the whole spectrum of actors involved in assessment and monitoring of plastic pollution, it is important to devote efforts to the understanding of the whole project and the important driver behind it – **the need for harmonization to allow time and space comparison, and status and effectiveness of measures implemented to tackle plastic pollution**. This level of overarching information will suit the whole set of stakeholders.

In addition, specialized information linked to the different WPs is necessary to engage adequately the different categories of stakeholders and ensure the legitimation and uptake of the results from each of the work packages and the whole project. For this the EUROqCHARM consortium is taking actions to engage specific stakeholder groups on a regular basis. These actions include:

- knowledge transfer of best practices concerning various issues related to plastic pollution monitoring
- information exchange between key actors from scientific institutions, industries, standardisation bodies and policy makers
- dissemination of recommendations for overcoming identified gaps and weaknesses which prevent effective monitoring

1.3. Relevant Project Bodies

Within EUROqCHARM there are several project bodies of relevance for communication, dissemination, and networking (Figure 2). Specifically:

The Steering Committee (SC), the decision-making body within EUROqCHARM, is also responsible for the overall successful project dissemination and communication through developing a plan for the use and dissemination results and preparing press releases and joint publications by the Consortium or proposed by the Funding Authority.

The Communication and Coordination Committee (hereafter CCC) was established in the first three months (Milestone 2) of the project to ensure appropriate coordination between the advisory level of the project (SABs, SSABS) and the operational level (WPs). The CCC actively ensures a proper linkage between the scientific objectives of the project and adequate dissemination activities beyond the project partners. The CCC is responsible for making sure the scientific objectives of the project are transposed into a variety of dissemination activities reaching out to the widest possible range of stakeholders beyond the project partners. The CCC is chaired by WPL 5 - Joan Fabres. The core team plays a key role in the dissemination and communication of activities carried out within the different WPs and by project partners. It also feeds information to the Newsroom (see below) and has responsibility for all social media. During the first project year the CCC developed the Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan (CSDP), advised on the design of the visual identity and derived products and identified strategic dissemination priorities, opportunities, and content. The CCC receives, actively requests and, harvests input for dissemination and communication outputs from WPLs and project partners, defines the communication output, which is developed and finalized by WP5 partners, quality-controlled and then distributed through the Newsroom.

The Newsroom unites communication representatives of all partners. Members of the Newsroom take care to distribute news items and their links through own existing institutional social media accounts (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram). This strategy is a win-win-win: 1) it maximises the number of people exposed to EUROqCHARM via dissemination actions by each of the partner organisations; 2) news officers (project partners) can easily translate and customise the messages for their networks; and 3) all news items link back to the information hub - the project website - which results in increased website traffic and a better search engine ranking. The interplay between the CCC and the Newsroom, both set up during the first six months of the project, ensures the flow of information and results from the project towards stakeholders. The Newsroom will increase its activity during the 2nd project year to match the demand for increased dissemination of project outputs.

The Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and the Standardisation and Stakeholders Advisory Board (SSAB) are instrumental in ensuring the achievement of all project objectives, the quality of the deliverables, dissemination and appropriate exploitation of the key outputs. When it comes to the dissemination and networking the SAB and the SSAB members will contribute to amplify the dissemination and awareness of the project and to the clustering process among the community of European stakeholders.

Figure 2. Management structure of EUROqCHARM

1.4. Communication and Dissemination Strategic and Planning Tools

In the first 4 months of the project, the CCC developed the EUROqCHARM Communications Strategy and Dissemination Plan (CSDP). More specifically, the CSDP lays out the background and methodology for developing the communication strategy and identifies the aims and objectives, target groups, tools and main activities for project communication. It also maps the timeline of project communications as well as the responsibilities for carrying out the strategy and implementing the plan. It was developed to provide a common understanding and approach to communication between the partners and external stakeholders.

Communication and dissemination activities are focused and intensified around the submission and distribution of key deliverables, achievement of milestones and recognition of project organized events. Table 1 summarizes, in chronological order, the deliverables and events of major significance together with the editions of the newsletter (see Section 2.3) and constitutes the timeline for the dissemination plan. Note that two of the events planned for 2022 will be rescheduled to accommodate for delays in aspects of the project related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 1. Timeline for the dissemination plan. The timeline includes deliverables, events of major significance (in bold) and editions of the newsletter (in italics). Items with a * indicate changes in the original schedule.

Deliverable /Task number	Deliverable / Event	WP No.	Lead partner	Type of deliverable / Activity	Dissemination level	Date of delivery / expected
D5.1	Launch and management of dedicated website and social media	5	ILVO	Websites etc.	Public	Feb 2021
<i>NL 1</i>	<i>Newsletter 1 (May 2021)</i>	5	ILVO	<i>Newsletter</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>May 2021</i>
<i>NL 2</i>	<i>Newsletter 2 (November 2021)</i>	5	ILVO	<i>Newsletter</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>Sept 2021</i>
D1.1	Critical review of methods and protocols for the analysis of nano-, micro- and macro- plastic in different environmental matrices	1	CNR	Report	Confidential	Jan 2022 -> March 2022*
<i>NL 3</i>	<i>Newsletter 3 (March 2022)</i>	5	ILVO	<i>Newsletter</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>March 2022</i>
5.2	Organisation of the workshop with stakeholders on the results from WP 1	5	ILVO	Workshop	By invitation / public	March 2022 -> May 2022*
5.3	Organisation of the workshop with international laboratories participating in the quality control study	5	VUA	Workshop	By invitation / public	May 2022 -> July 2022*
D2.1	Evaluation on the results of the interlaboratory study	2	VUA	Report	Confidential	July 2022
D2.2	Feasibility study of the harmonised protocol for use in large scale monitoring programs	2	NIVA	Report	Public	Aug 2022
<i>NL 4</i>	<i>Newsletter 4 (September 2022)</i>	5	ILVO	<i>Newsletter</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>Sept 2022</i>
D3.1	Recommendations of procedures and methods for monitoring programs	3	AU	Report	Public	Oct 2022
5.4	Organisation of the workshop – “Sampling strategies for plastic litter (from macro to micro and nanoplastics) monitoring in the different environmental compartments”	5	SALT	Workshop	By invitation / public	Jan 2023
D4.1	Report on the establishment of Operational Network for Plastic monitoring	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	Feb 2023
<i>NL 5</i>	<i>Newsletter 3 (March 2023)</i>	5	ILVO	<i>Newsletter</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>March 2023</i>
D3.2	Optimisation of monitoring strategies to improve the MSFD strategy	3	IFREMER	Report	Public	April 2023
D4.2	Handbook of relevant European plastic monitoring entities, projects and initiatives	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	June 2023
D3.3	Standard measuring procedures for policy and legislation (baselines and thresholds)	3	NIVA	Report	Public	Aug 2023
D3.4	Report on global database synchronisation	3	OGS	Report	Public	Aug 2023
D4.3	Report on development of national and regional plastic litter capacity building action plans	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	Aug 2023
<i>NL 6</i>	<i>Newsletter 4 (September 2023)</i>	5	ILVO	<i>Newsletter</i>	<i>Public</i>	<i>Sept 2023</i>
D4.4	Report on the Transnational Joint Actions	4	INCDM-NIMRD	Report	Public	Oct 2023
D2.3	Production of at least two CRMs, and identification of two candidate CRMs	2	CHIRON	Other	Public	Oct 2023
5.6	Organisation of the EUROqCHARM Final conference	5	NIVA	Conference	Public	Oct 2023

Also during the first project year, the CCC team has initiated the development of a stakeholder's engagement strategy, aimed at (i) facilitating the knowledge transfer and strengthening/enabling capacity building on harmonized methods and standards for assessment and monitoring of plastic pollution, (ii) creating an international community, including diverse stakeholders' groups that strive towards the harmonization of such methods and standards in a joint effort to tackle plastic pollution.

The very first draft of stakeholders' strategy covers aspects like: type of stakeholders, stakeholders influence, prioritization of stakeholders, mechanisms and tools for stakeholders' engagement, type of content and content appropriateness according to the stakeholder group involved, frequency and type of engagement expected from the various stakeholder groups mapped as relevant for the EUROqCHARM community.

2. Communication, Dissemination and Networking Activities

The following sections describe the major communication and dissemination tools and activities developed and implemented during the project's first year and the corresponding impact monitoring and assessment mechanisms.

During the first year, there were more than 60 communication and dissemination activities, going from journal articles, website texts, and webinar presentations to social media posts.

2.1. Visual Identity

The **logo** is the basis of the visual identity and reflects three important characteristics of the project: It concerns plastic litter and its degradation products; it is focused on research methodology and it is a European initiative. The logo is a combination of the project acronym and a visual element: the letter Q depicted as a magnifying glass showing plastic degrading into microplastics.

The logo is available in colour, in black and white, and in negative (white logo for coloured backgrounds) (Figure 3). The logo is being used across all EUROqCHARM communication products including deliverables, reports and presentations by partners at conferences and other physical and online events. All project partners are encouraged to use the logo in any correspondence (e.g. email signatures) while working on the project.

In addition to the logo, the wave included in the central part of the logo has been used as the other main visual identity coupled to the project. This extra visual element complements the logo and can be used to create visual coherence in derived products.

Figure 3. EUROqCHARM logo and graphical element

To strengthen the visibility of the project and the association of the project results with the project itself, a series of templates have been made available for use for all project outputs.

All **presentations** about EUROqCHARM or its results use the EUROqCHARM presentation template. The template provides the EUROqCHARM visuals and suggestions for text formatting (Figure 4). Project partners are free to add logo and name of the institute of their affiliation.

A template **word document** (Figure 5) is provided with a fixed header and footer, and a document version tracker. This template is to be used as the basic template for internal and external reports, meeting agenda and minutes etc.

As most meetings during the first year of the project were held online due to COVID restrictions, a Microsoft Teams **background** (Figure 6) was provided for all partners in EUROqCHARM style.

Figure 4. EUROqCHARM Microsoft Powerpoint Presentation template

Figure 5. EUROqCHARM Microsoft Word document template

Figure 6. EUROqCHARM Teams video background

The visual identity was mostly developed during the first six project months but will be used and potentially further developed during the rest of project activities and products, e.g. invitations for events, printed flyers for use during events. Depending on COVID-19 pandemic, EUROqCHARM plans for printed promotion to be used during physical events.

A visually attractive **flyer** (Figure 7) reflecting the essence of the project has been made available to all partners in digital and printable format (up to A0 for use as a poster).

Standardization of methods to measure plastic pollution by 2024?
EUROqCHARM faces up to the challenge

© F. Gaigani

The ambitious goal of the European project, **EUROqCHARM**, is to establish harmonized methodologies for the monitoring and assessment of macro-, micro- and nanoplastics in the environment, as well as blueprints for standards and recommendations for policy and legislation.

More specifically, EUROqCHARM will evaluate existing methodologies for plastic pollution assessments, harmonize them on a European level - with rigorous quality control - and reinforce the European monitoring capacities based on the developed guidelines. The goal is to achieve this for **plastic debris, microplastics and nanoplastics** in freshwater and seawater, in soil and seafloor sediment, in living organisms, and in the air. The project will deliver the necessary and very urgent **methodological support** that is needed to successfully implement long-term strategies to deal with plastic pollution.

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www.euroqcharm.eu

euroqcharm@niva.no
twitter: @EUROqCHARM

Figure 7. EUROqCHARM project flyer

2.2. Project Website

EUROqCHARM has its own website that can be accessed at www.euroqcharm.eu. The website provides basic information on the project. It is intended as a platform for providing updates on project activity and disseminating outputs in addition to providing relevant news and facilitating contacts for the project, its WPs and each of its partners. The website is continuously updated based on top-down input by the project management and bottom-up input by experts involved in the project. The website is set up to be bilingual, with an English version and a French version (the French version of the website was launched in June 2021). Translation is coordinated by the website manager. The quality control of the English version is provided by NIVA while AFNOR quality controls the French version. The project website is hosted and maintained by ILVO. A screenshot of EUROqCHARM website homepage is provided in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Screenshot of EUROqCHARM’s website homepage

The effectiveness of dissemination through the website will be periodically analysed. The EUROqCHARM webpage will be tracked by means of Google Analytics. ILVO will build in Google Analytics on each website page to track number of visits and more specifically geographic location, origin (direct search, social media, ...), bounce rate, time spent on website and number of unique and repeated visits. These functionalities will be implemented during the first quarter of the second project year, i.e. by the end of 2021.

During the first year of EUROqCHARM, three news items were published on the website (Figure 9). One of them was the project kick-off press release, aimed at informing a broad audience about the project’s kick-off and focus, two focused on the methodology literature review, targeting a more specialized audience likely interested in the details of the work being carried out under WP1, and one on the participation of one of the project members in a EUROqCHARM relevant scientific conference.

Figure 9. Screenshots of news items on the EUROqCHARM website

The impossibility to celebrate a physical kick-off meeting and inviting the media to cover it was countered by the publication of the kick-off press release as a website article on the EUROqCHARM and partner websites (Figure 10). These texts were picked up by journalists and were translated into articles published on other websites (Figure 11).

During the second year, we expect more frequent publications of news items, as the first project results become available and more (stakeholder) events and workshops will be organised. All upcoming news items are written by the communications team, and quality controlled by the scientists, work package leader in question and, the CCC. The bilingual (EN/FR) approach will be

maintained. The website designer will operationalize the analytical tools in function of reporting and optimisation of the website posts.

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche IT | EN Cerca

Scienze biomediche Chimica e tecnologia materiali
 Terra e ambiente Ingegneria, ICT, energia e trasporti
 Fisica e materia Scienze umane e patrimonio culturale
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NEWS

Il Cnr-Ismar pronto alla sfida di "EUROqCHARM" per uniformare i metodi di misura dell'inquinamento da plastica

23/12/2020

L'obiettivo ambizioso del progetto europeo "EUROqCHARM", di recente avvio, è stabilire metodologie armonizzate per il monitoraggio e la valutazione di macro, micro e nanoplastiche nell'ambiente, nonché schemi standard e raccomandazioni per politiche e normative. L'Istituto di scienze marine (Ismar) del Cnr è nella compagine dei 15 partner, attori chiave coinvolti nello studio e nel monitoraggio dell'inquinamento da plastica in Europa, sotto il coordinamento dell'Istituto norvegese per la ricerca sull'acqua (Niva).

Più specificamente, il progetto valuterà le metodologie esistenti per la valutazione dell'inquinamento da plastica, le armonizzerà a livello europeo - con un rigoroso controllo di qualità - e rafforzerà le capacità di monitoraggio europee sulla base delle linee guida sviluppate: lo scopo è di raggiungere questo obiettivo per i rifiuti di plastica, le microplastiche e le nanoplastiche nell'acqua dolce e marina, nel suolo e nei sedimenti del fondo marino, negli organismi viventi e nell'aria. Il progetto fornirà il supporto metodologico necessario e molto urgente per attuare con successo strategie a lungo termine per affrontare l'inquinamento da plastica.

Spazzatura sulla spiaggia, accumuli di immondizia nell'oceano, microplastiche negli alimenti, particelle di polvere di plastica nell'aria: ci sono ampie prove oggi che l'inquinamento da plastica è diffuso e sta minacciando la fauna selvatica, l'ambiente marino, acquatico e terrestre e la salute umana. Di conseguenza, ha guadagnato un'attenzione significativa nell'agenda dei politici, del mondo accademico, dei media e della società in generale. Ancora più importante, vi è ora un diffuso consenso verso l'azione, che dovrebbe tradursi in strategie per mitigare l'inquinamento da plastica e i suoi effetti a lungo termine e solide.

Questo processo, tuttavia, richiede una conoscenza approfondita del problema dell'inquinamento da plastica, basata su metodi di campionamento, analisi e comunicazione standardizzati e intercambiabili. Ma il cuore del problema è che le materie plastiche nell'ambiente sono attualmente campionate, analizzate e segnalate in molti modi diversi in tutto il mondo. Inoltre questi metodi si stanno evolvendo rapidamente. Dieci anni fa, ad esempio, era pratica comune eseguire una digestione a base acida e una successiva scansione visiva (stereoscopio). In questo momento, i metodi vanno verso la digestione basata su enzimi e la spettroscopia avanzata ad alta risoluzione come μ FTIR, μ RAMAN, o anche SEM-EDX (Scanning Electron Microscopy & Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy) in grado di rilevare particelle più piccole di 1 micrometro.

La mancanza di metodi armonizzati per la raccolta e la comunicazione dei dati rappresenta un grosso ostacolo all'attuazione delle azioni di monitoraggio e mitigazione. Ciò è ulteriormente ostacolato dalla mancanza di linee guida chiare sullo scopo di questi sforzi di monitoraggio.

Bert van Bavel, coordinatore del progetto per Niva afferma: "EUROqCHARM esaminerà criticamente i metodi analitici all'avanguardia e, facendo un ulteriore passo avanti nell'armonizzazione, li convaliderà attraverso confronti interlaboratori. Importanti laboratori di analisi della plastica ambientale andranno verso una unificazione dei metodi con produzione di materiali di riferimento certificati. Il trasferimento delle conoscenze sarà facilitato mediante seminari e rafforzamento delle capacità per i paesi che devono ancora avviare il monitoraggio".

I partner italiani sono Cnr-Ismar e Ogs: il Cnr, in particolare, contribuirà al progetto con le sue competenze sull'inquinamento da plastica in ambiente marino e colonna d'acqua. Spiega Stefano Aliani (Cnr-Ismar): "Dagli anni '90 i nostri studi si concentrano sulla diffusione di detriti marini e microplastiche nell'ambiente marino. Siamo lieti di poter contribuire con la nostra esperienza a questo grande progetto di armonizzazione internazionale che cambierà l'approccio al monitoraggio".

Altra ricaduta del progetto, la creazione di una rete di comunicazione composta da scienziati e varie tipologie di stakeholders per consentire la cooperazione e lo sviluppo del dialogo, del processo decisionale e dell'attuazione delle soluzioni. A tal fine, "EUROqCHARM" riunisce le aree di ricerca pertinenti: nell'ambito delle scienze naturali sono incluse le scienze marine, le acque sotterranee, le acque potabili e di scarico, il suolo, l'aria; la chimica analitica ecc.). Per l'industria partecipano produttori di strumenti, produttori di plastica e laboratori commerciali insieme a politici e organismi internazionali quali Nazioni Unite, UE, organismi di standardizzazione, associazioni e società professionali, politici (ONU, UE e livello nazionale) e organizzazioni non governative (ONG) nazionali e internazionali.

Una vasta azione sinergica che pone l'Europa in una posizione unica per coordinare la validazione dei metodi disponibili e lo sviluppo di protocolli armonizzati per la valutazione della contaminazione da plastica: in questo modo sarà possibile un vero confronto dei dati, che costituirà la base per le linee guida e le normative europee e internazionali di riferimento per il futuro per ridurre l'impatto ambientale dell'inquinamento da plastica.

EUROqCHARM partners

ILVO, AWI, CSIC, AMBA UNIVERSITY, Ifremer, VU, CNR ISMAR, NIVA, NILU, afnor, OGS, eawag

Il Progetto è finanziato dal Programma Europeo Horizon 2020

Partnership del progetto EuroqCharm

Figure 10. Screenshot of the article about EUROqCHARM published on partner (CNR) website in Italian.

Figure 11. Screenshot of the article about EUROqCHARM published in “Norway Today”

2.3. Newsletter

EUROqCHARM has opted for a periodic newsletter as a more direct tool for dissemination of the project activities and results to the stakeholders. It allows for active, attention targeted and regular distribution of news to the subscribers. Stakeholders can easily subscribe to the newsletter using a website link. Newsletter subscription has been promoted in all project communication activities by distributing the subscription link.

The [first Newsletter](#) was issued in May 2021 (Figure 12) and was sent to 102 subscribers, with an open rate of almost 60% and a click rate of 35%. The second Newsletter will be sent to at least 122 subscribers during November 2021.

In the second project year, two editions of the Newsletter will be issued: one in spring (ca. March 2022) and one in autumn (ca. September 2022). Subscription to the newsletter will be continuously promoted to encourage new readers to follow the EUROqCHARM progress.

Figure 12. Header and introduction of the first edition of the EUROqCHARM newsletter

2.4. Social Media

Social media as a communication tool is mainly used within EUROqCHARM to reach research institutes and commercial laboratories, environmental agencies, decision-makers, data-owners and managers, and the private sector. To date, three platforms have been activated, namely Twitter, ResearchGate and LinkedIn.

2.4.1. Twitter

The EUROqCHARM consortium has a Twitter account [@EUROqCHARM](https://twitter.com/EUROqCHARM), launched on 25th February 2021. The Twitter account is used to provide updates on ongoing work, announce events organized or attended by EUROqCHARM partners, disseminate results and publications and to network with relevant projects, initiatives and stakeholders. The account is managed by Amy Lusher (NIVA) and Joan Fabres (SALT). Content aimed for dissemination through Twitter is provided by all partners to the CCC by providing suggested Twitter message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and

background information (links or documents). Partners and experts with own Twitter accounts are asked to interact with EUROqCHARM by tagging to strengthen the messaging and to broaden the reach. The success of the account is monitored using the built-in Twitter statistics (number of followers and number of posts and the number of “impressions” and “total engagements” per post, (Table 2). The quality of the posts is monitored by the CCC.

The EUROqCHARM Twitter account [@EUROqCHARM](https://twitter.com/EUROqCHARM) has 147 followers and has posted 24 original tweets (as of 28 Oct 2021). Tweets have a general reach of hundreds to several thousands of users (Table 2). The inaugural tweet promoting the project website was the best received followed by tweets targeting the fundamental questions that the project is addressing and sharing insight derived from the analyses done by the project experts (Figure 13) or announcing contributions at meetings/conferences.

During the second year, the Twitter network will be expanded, and regular tweets will be sent out. NIVA and SALT will continue to feed the account with original news and interaction within the network, with the support of ILVO and the EUROqCHARM scientists. A planning mechanism has been setup during the first project year to prepare and review news items.

Table 2. Twitter Analytics as of 29.10.2021. Data extracted from Twitter Analytics providing information on the outreach of each of the tweets published by @EUROqCHARM. Impressions and total engagements provide sense of outreach and reaction to it

Date of original post	Screen shot	Impressions	Total engagements	Likes	Retweets	Detail expands	Media engagements	Profile clicks	Link clicks	Replies	Hashtag clicks	Votes
25.02.2021		8,190	210	19	11	75	40	34	30	1	0	-
12.03.2021		3,919	167	20	8	33	73	23	9	1	1	-
08.04.2021		2,326	197	25	5	19	115	33	-	-	-	-
06.05.2021		860	29	1	3	15	-	2	-	1	1	6
01.06.2021		483	16	4	1	7	1	3	-	-	-	-

Date of original post	Screen shot	Impressions	Total engagements	Likes	Retweets	Detail expands	Media engagements	Profile clicks	Link clicks	Replies	Hashtag clicks	Votes
31.07.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM #ICESASC21 (6-10 sept) will host a session on marine litter, co-chaired by http://www.EUROqCHARM.eu partner F. Galgani of @Ifremer_fr. Join to exchange on common interests such as updated approaches and methods for the assessment and monitoring of #marinelitter and #microplastics! pic.twitter.com/GA3jpCDFg</p>	924	34	10	5	5	10	1	1	-	2	-
03.19.2021 *retweet	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM It's great to see this international #collaboration published. EUROqCHARM is closely following developments around methods in #plastics research. #validated methodologies in plastics and rubber particle research are needed for #harmonized monitoring approaches. https://twitter.com/DianaElisabeth/status/1433686317938921481 ...</p>	126	3	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
07.09.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM Registered for the 2nd International Akademie Fresenius Conference on #microplastics? Don't miss the afternoon session of Sept 10th on harmonised identification of microplastics by http://www.EUROqCHARM.eu, Amy Lusher! https://www.akademie-fresenius.com/events/detail/produkt/international-akademie-fresenius-conference-microplastics-online-conference-1/ ... pic.twitter.com/NyCtCTcbg2</p>	342	26	7	3	8	2	1	7	1	-	-
08.09.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM Bet van Bavel from @NIVAforskning will present tomorrow! @EU_ScienceHub (JRC) virtual Symposium on "Challenges of microplastics analysis – Bridging state of the art and policy needs" and introduce work we do @EUROqCHARM https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/event/workshop/challenges-microplastic-analysis ...</p>	683	27	6	2	9	-	6	6	-	-	-
17.09.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM No pressure at all 😊 after hearing about the results from several interlaboratory studies at @EU_ScienceHub (JRC) workshop on "Challenges on #microplastic #analysis". High expectations from #researchers & @EU_Commission #policymakers. @EUROqCHARM stands up to the challenge 🙌 pic.twitter.com/kocrD1R9an</p>	215	17	5	-	5	6	1	-	-	-	-
17.09.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM Bienvenue chez @EUROqCHARM ! Maintenant, vous pouvez également suivre notre #H2020 projet via notre site français FR https://www.euroqcharm.eu/fr #PollutionPlastique #environnement @HorizonEU pic.twitter.com/ztkLg0MJyc</p>	683	36	2	2	21	6	2	3	-	-	-
12.10.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM Is #plasticpollution research evolving fast enough? 😊 @EUROqCHARM is gathering evidence that the most used assessment/monitoring methods may not always be the best. Brainstorming 🧠 on the methods' systematic review at work (in the same room!)@NIVAforskning ok. Stay tuned for more! pic.twitter.com/Wmk3qr3lXB</p>	2,358	204	34	10	48	90	20	-	2	-	-
18.10.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM thoroughly analyzed methods described within 660 📄 papers on beach litter and microplastics in sediments. "Stats work is underway but size classes will definitely need alignment to come up with best suited" says Jakob Strand @AarhusUni #plasticpollution #harmonization pic.twitter.com/b4076dgKKc</p>	442	33	9	3	4	15	-	1	1	-	-
21.10.2021	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM Methods for quantifying #microplastics in biota have evolved markedly in the last decade, and still are! "SWOT analyses on existing methods and defining minimal requirements will lead us to the best suited ones", says Bavo de Witte from @ILVOvlaanderen #plasticpollution @EU_ENV pic.twitter.com/6v5Aal8Atx</p>	635	50	12	4	9	18	5	-	1	1	-
26.10.2021 (1/2)	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM Thanks Stefano (@CNRsocial_) for the progress update on #systematicreview of #plasticpollution assessment methods las thursday @EUROqCHARM yr 1 partner meeting.. We are getting there! pic.twitter.com/TSdl8g9WRq</p>	396	30	6	3	5	13	2	-	1	-	-
26.10.2021 (2/2)	<p>EUROqCHARM @EUROqCHARM And our #stakeholders should be hearing about it soon pic.twitter.com/1cwaalUnUg1</p>	46	4	1	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	-

Figure 13. Examples of Twitter posts from the EUROqCHARM Twitter account

2.4.2. ResearchGate

The EUROqCHARM consortium has a ResearchGate project page that was launched in February 2021 by NIVA. The page is used to provide updates on ongoing work, announce events organized or attended by EUROqCHARM partners, disseminate results and publications. The target audience of ResearchGate are research scientists actively involved in plastic pollution research. The account is managed by the Scientific Project Manager, Amy Lusher (NIVA) and all project partners with active ResearchGate accounts are added as collaborators providing a link to their laboratories. Content aimed for dissemination through ResearchGate will be provided by all partners to the Newsroom by providing suggested message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and background information (links or documents). Partners with their own ResearchGate accounts are asked to interact with EUROqCHARM by tagging the project in order to strengthen the messaging and to broaden the reach. The quality of the posts is monitored by the CCC. The project now has 29 followers (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Screen capture of the EUROqCHARM ResearchGate page

2.4.3. LinkedIn

The project does not have a dedicated LinkedIn page. Posts shared on Twitter and Research Gate are modified to allow project partners to share project updates on their personal or institutional LinkedIn accounts (Figure 15). Content aimed for dissemination through LinkedIn is provided by all partners to the Newsroom by providing suggested LinkedIn message, graphical content (picture, illustration, short video) and background information (links or documents). The quality of the posts is monitored by the CCC.

Figure 15. Screen capture of the LinkedIn page of Amy Lusher. The post announcing the launch of the project website had received 1,296 views, 2 reshares as of 28.10.20201.

2.5. Scientific Publications

Publishing the work and results of EUROqCHARM is essential to meet project objectives and reach the wide audience envisioned and to ensure a high impact of the project. Partners are encouraged to communicate about EUROqCHARM in public venues and publish the results obtained through the project.

During the first year, EUROqCHARM experts contributed to the production and publication of two papers that included or built on the results and analysis carried out in the project. The two publications are listed below and the EUROqCHARM members are depicted with * and highlighted in bold type.

- **Lusher, A.L.***, Hurley, R., Arp, H.P.H., Booth, A.M., Bråte, I.L.N., Gabrielsen, G.W., Gomiero, A., Gomes, T., Grøsvik, B.E., Green, N., Haave, M., Hallanger, I.G., Halsband, C., **Herzke, D.***, Joner, E.J., Kogel, T., Rakkestad, K., Ranneklev, S.B, Wagner. M., Olsen, M. (2021). Moving forward in microplastic Research: A Norwegian perspective. *Environment International*, 157, p. 106794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106794>.
- Martin, J., **Lusher, A.L.***, Nixon, F.C., 2021. A review of the use of microplastics in reconstructing dated sedimentary archives. *Science of The Total Environment*, 150818. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.150818>.

2.6. Events as Communication Tools

A large part of the dissemination and communication activities (more than 60) were virtual events making up for the limited direct interaction due to COVID restrictions. The advantage of this kind of events is that a large audience is reached and that often a digital record of the events is available for viewing after the event time has passed allowing for a larger and longer outreach than the physical events. The events organized were targeting three different kinds of audiences and stakeholders, namely the European Commission and connected initiatives or forums, the international scientific and monitoring community and finally, industry actors. Below follows a description of the different events attended by project members that included active EUROqCHARM dissemination efforts.

2.6.1. EUROqCHARM dissemination activities towards the European Commission

The PC attended two online cluster meetings organised by the European Research Executive Agency (REA): REA Unit B.3 “Biodiversity, Circular Economy and Environment”. The purpose of the first meeting (1st June 2021) was to bring together the project coordinators of projects dealing with marine litter from different angles including (1) providing harmonisation of procedures for plastic pollution monitoring and assessments (EUROqCHARM), (2) providing sustainable alternatives to plastics currently used for different applications ([SEALIVE](#), [BIO-PLASTICS EUROPE](#)), or (3) developing technologies to remove litter and (micro)plastics from the oceans and seas ([CLAIM](#), [GoJelly](#), [MAELSTROM](#), [In-No-Plastic](#), [LABPLAS](#)). The purpose of the second meeting (30th September 2021) was to bring together the project coordinators of 11 projects which have aspects related to the EU Plastics Strategy including (1) transitions to the circular economy ([JUST2CE](#)), (2) tackling plastic pollution (EUROqCHARM, [LABPLAS](#)), (3) plastics in agriculture ([PAPILLONS](#), [MINAGRIS](#)), (4) improving the sorting, separation and recycling of composite and multi-layer materials ([MERLIN](#), [CIMPA](#), [Sol-Rec2](#), [CIRCULAR FoodPak](#)), and (5) circular systems in plastics, textiles and furniture sectors ([SCIRT](#), [CISUFLO](#)).

2.6.2. EUROqCHARM Dissemination Activities Towards the Scientific and Monitoring Community

There have been more than 15 interactions targeting the scientific and monitoring community and some examples are:

- Presentation at the NORMAN Network WG4 Meeting – 17th November 2020
- Presentation to Scientific community at Micro2020 – 23-27th November 2020
- Presentation at the NORMAN Network General Assembly – 2nd December 2020
- Presentation to the OSPAR Expert Working Group – 14th January 2021

- Inclusion in sessions and panel discussions during the SETAC Seminar Series – Microplastics in Humans and the Environment – 16th March- 6th April 2021
- Presentation to the Norwegian Environment Agency – Norwegian Seminar on Microplastics: Current Knowledge Status on Sources, Effects and Risk – 7- 8th April 2021
- Dedicated session, presentations, poster and panel discussion at SETAC EUROPE – 4th May 2021
- Presentation at the European Workshop on Microplastics – 20th May 2021
- Inclusion in “plastica aleternativa”. A “blue appetizer” which was part of the festival “maredirefare” dedicated to the ocean Decade, Trieste, Italy – 15th June 2021
- Presentation to the MSFD Technical Group Marine Litter – 22 - 23rd June 2021
- Attendance at MSFD Technical Group Marine Litter – Micro-litter workshop 26 -27th October 2021

As an example, and to provide better understanding of the scope of this type of events we provide details on the last event listed above. Sebastian Primpke (AWI) and Amy Lusher (NIVA) co-chaired a session during the SETAC Europe Annual Meeting. The session titled “Harmonized data reporting and analyses in micro- and nano-plastics research” was specifically crafted to support activities in EUROqCHARM and inform the European/international scientific community of the project. The PC along with EUROqCHARM WP leaders presented a status of their work and participated in a live discussion session. A poster of EUROqCHARM was also made available to describe the project (Figure 16). There were over 150 participants to the session.

EUROCHARM

Standardization of methods to measure plastic pollution by 2024?

EUROqCHARM faces up to the challenge

Contact: Amy Lusher
EUROqCHARM Project Manager
EUROqCHARM@niva.no
Norwegian Institute for Water Research (NIVA)

EUROqCHARM will use a multi-stakeholder approach to identify and develop cost-effective monitoring strategies for plastics (nano-, micro-, macro-) in all environmental matrices.

EUROqCHARM will facilitate developments for European plastic monitoring programmes and the realization of international best-practices.

Goals:

- Provide a platform to discuss and validate methods for monitoring of plastics in environmental samples.
- Develop blueprints for standardization.
- Recommend revision of current EU policies and instruments.

How?

- EUROqCHARM will evaluate existing methods for the assessment of plastic pollution.
- Harmonize these methods on a European level - with rigorous quality control - and reinforce European monitoring capacities.

Why?

- Major actions to evaluate, optimize and harmonize monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution are urgently needed.
- This will support substantial improvements in international environmental sustainability and socio-economic development

EUROqCHARM will deliver the necessary methodological harmonization to successfully implement long-term strategies for combating plastic pollution.

Scan to access www.euroqcharm.eu and sign up for our newsletter

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 coordination and support action under grant agreement No. 101000805 (EUROqCHARM). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Partners: NIVA, ILVO, AWI, VU, Ifremer, eawag, OGS, afnor, CSIC, NILU, and others.

Figure 16. EUROqCHARM Poster prepared for the SETAC Europe meeting, May 2021

2.6.3. EUROqCHARM Dissemination Activities Towards to Industry

The PC held a series of meetings with potential stakeholders and showcased EUROqCHARM during these presentations. The two examples below were presentations given at fora with strong representation of the analytical instrument industry

- ThermoFischer Scientific Science for Sustainability Symposium – 13-15th April 2021
- Perkin Elmer Global Environmental Summit – 4th June 2021

2.6.4. Events Planned for the Second Project Year

To ensure dissemination and stakeholder involvement, the EUROqCHARM consortium will organise 3 workshops and a final event involving participation from outside the consortium (Tasks 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 and 5.6). Two of the three workshops are planned for the second project year.

- a workshop (Task 5.2) with stakeholders to communicate the results of WP1. This will be organised by ILVO, in close cooperation with NIVA, SALT and the Work Package 1 Leader.
- a workshop (Task 5.3) with international laboratories participating in the quality control study. This will be organised by VUA, in close cooperation with NIVA, SALT.

The events will be widely announced and promoted using the available tools (website, newsletter, Twitter, etc.). During and after the events, consortium members will be encouraged to provide testimonials on progress and results, pictures and footage to the Newsroom. This input can then be translated in news items for dissemination of the main outcomes.

Additionally, EUROqCHARM plans to participate in external specialized events with oral presentations and participation in panel discussions. The indicative list at the time of writing this report includes:

- SETAC Europe Copenhagen 15-19 May 2022– Session proposal (pending abstract submission) (Primpke, Lusher, Kallenbach). Micro- and nano-plastics: Towards the harmonized analysis for monitoring, effect studies and risk assessment.
- Microplastics Reference Material Workshop, Feb 9-10, 2022, Atlanta, Georgia. United States - Lusher invited attendee. It will be attended by 35 representatives of academia, government, and industry and the expected output is an open access scientific journal article that outlines a framework strategy for creating a MP reference materials repository and recommended materials. This publication will further serve as a “state of the science” for MPs reference materials.
- Ministry of Environment Japan (MOEJ) International Expert Meeting on marine plastic litter monitoring data sharing project - 29th November 2021 – Online (Lusher and Galgani).

In addition to the events listed above as part of the project communication and dissemination timeline, the project Annual Meetings and General Assembly meetings are also of significance as their occurrence is worth reporting outside the project consortium. They constitute opportunities for interaction amongst project partners for the discussion of communication and dissemination activities. Table 3 provides the timing for these meetings.

Table 3. Timeline for major project meetings with dissemination significance. The events highlighted in bold are planned for the second project year.

	Meeting Type	Date	Location (partner)
KOM	Kick off meeting	12.11.2020	Online (NIVA)
GEA 1	Ordinary General Assembly 1	16.12.2020	Online (NIVA)
AM 1	First year Annual Meeting	21.10.2020	Online (NIVA)
GEA 2	Ordinary General Assembly 2	21.10.2020	Online (NIVA)
AM 2	Second year annual meeting	M24	TBC
GEA 3	Ordinary General Assembly 3	M24	TBC
AM 3	Third year annual and final meeting	M36	Brussels (NIVA)

2.7. Monitoring and Assessment of Impact

To ensure a timely reporting on the potential impact of the project, the EUROqCHARM CCC has developed a template for partners to record their dissemination and exploitation activities.

The reporting template provides guidance and covers aspects such as: target group, size of audience and partner(s) involved. Impact reporting is complex but at the very least the approximate size of the audience reached is very important specially when activities are time intensive and involving active communication like presentations, workshops or seminars. In addition to impact information, details of the event through links to the announcement/programme, files of the dissemination product and if possible graphical documentation (pictures or screenshots if the event is digital) are provided.

Statistics and information have been collected from over 60 different activities registered onto the dissemination log (Figure 17), with 29 activities taking place in 2021. These activities include the following types: Direct emails, Discussion, Exhibitions, Launch of the website/wiki, Poster, Social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, etc.), Web article, Webinar presentation. Considering the COVID-19 pandemic, it is not surprising to find that all these activities took place online. Contributions have been made by the following partners: CNR, CNR-ISMAR, ILVO, NILU, NIVA, OGS, SALT. Activities and/or events took place in the following languages: English, English/Italian, English/Japanese, Flemish, Italian, Norwegian. Audience size for these activities/events ranged from a minimum of one audience member (e.g., Webinar presentation with SAB member Chelsea Rochman and Discussion with ThermoFischer) to a maximum of 25,500 (e.g., Web article in Flemish on Engineeringnet).

Below follows a list of the different media and fora used in the dissemination activities which provides insight on the variety of platforms used for the dissemination efforts in EUROqCHARM. The further development of the stakeholder strategy will inform which of these platforms should be prioritized for dissemination efforts during the rest of the project life. CNR Website, Eco - environment coastal & offshore, EMODnet Chemistry portal, Engineeringnet, EUROqCHARM Kick-off Meeting, EUROqCHARM Twitter account, EUROqCHARM Website, Ministry of Environment Japan Expert Meeting, EMODNet Chemistry Website, ILVO Website, ISO/CEN, Marine Recycling Cluster Website, MICRO2020, mynewsdesk.com/NIVA, NILU Website, NIVA Facebook, NIVA Lunch Seminar, NIVA Website, NODC/OGS website, Norman Network, Norman Network General Assembly, Norman Network General Assembly (Virtual Exhibition), Norway Today Website, Norwegian Environment Agency, REVOcean Website, SAB Kick off, SALT Facebook, SALT Website, SETAC Europe 31st Annual Meeting, SETAC Seminar Series Microplastics, Standard Norway, Standard Norway (Norsk komité SN/K 153 Vannkvalitet), Tekfisk.no, ThermoFischer.

Record #	Partner organisation	Author/presenter	Others involved	Activity type	Title	Event / source name	Target group	Language
34	NIVA	A. Lusher	e	Twitter, etc.)	EUROqCHARM research is in full swing	account	All stakeholders	English
35	SALT	H. Redås	J. Fabres	Social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, etc.)	SALT er en del av EUROqCHARM prosjektet som skal bidra til standardisering av metoder for vurdering og overvåking av plastforurensning på europeisk nivå	SALT Facebook	All stakeholders	Norwegian
36	NIVA	A. Lusher	J. Fabres, S. Vandendriessche	Social media (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, etc.)	Is it possible to map out all the methods used for plastic pollution assessment and monitoring?	EUROqCHARM Twitter account	All stakeholders	English
37	NIVA	A. Lusher		Webinar presentation	Towards the Harmonized Identification of Microplastics	SETAC Seminar Series Microplastics	Scientific Community	English
38	NIVA	A. Lusher	S. Primpke	Webinar presentation	Problem formulation: What we know and what we need to know: the Analytic, monitoring and effects of micropalstics in Humans and the Environment	SETAC Seminar Series Microplastics	Scientific Community	English
39	NIVA	A. Lusher	Bert van Bavel, S. Primpke	Discussion	Harmonisation in plastic pollution research	SETAC Seminar Series Microplastics	Scientific Community	English
40	NIVA	B.v Bavel		Webinar presentation	EUROqCHARM- EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution	Standard Norway (Norsk komité SN/K 153 Vannkvalitet)	Scientific Community	Norwegian
41	NIVA	A.Lusher		Webinar presentation	EUROqCHARM- EUROpean quality Controlled Harmonization Assuring Reproducible Monitoring and assessment of plastic pollution	Norwegian Environment Agency	All stakeholders	English
42	NIVA	A.Lusher	S. Primpke	Discussion	Harmonized Data Reporting and Analyses in Micro- and Nanoplastics Research	SETAC Europe 31st Annual Meeting	Scientific Community	English
43	NIVA	A.Lusher		Discussion	EUROqCHARM - Assuring Reproducible, Harmonised and	SETAC Europe 31st Annual Meeting	Scientific Community	English

Figure 17. Screen capture of the dissemination log

3. Conclusion

Communication activities during the first year of EUROqCHARM were intensive, with the development of the visual identity and the set-up of its dedicated website and social media channels. The visual identity was developed and straightforwardly applied to all EUROqCHARM products.

At the beginning of the project, a press release was drafted and distributed that was published on many institutional websites, and that resulted in a several articles in professional journals and magazines.

News on the progress of EUROqCHARM was monitored and harvested by the CCC, and was translated in different messages targeting different channels, i.e. website, newsletter and social media. This resulted in three news items on the website, 20 Twitter posts and one newsletter. A second newsletter will be issued at the beginning of November 2021.

During the second year, it is expected that the pace of communication will increase, as more project results become available. News will feed into the website, two newsletters and regular tweets. In addition, two major events are planned which will be partially organized and reported on by SALT and ILVO.

The communications log will be maintained and continue to be updated to track communication and dissemination actions conducted by all partners.

As for communication, the CCC has established a workflow that will continue to be used in future communication planning.

APPENDIX 1: REFERENCES AND RELATED DOCUMENTS

ID	Reference or Related Document	Source or Link/Location
1	EUROqCHARM Deliverable 5.1 Launch and management of dedicated website and social media	
2	Communication Strategy and Dissemination Plan	<i>Annexed to Deliverable 5.1 in working form</i>

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